

COMPREHENSIVE SURVEY AND SOLUTIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE OLD CITY MAHALLAS IN TASHKENT

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Annotatsiya

This article is devoted to historical mahallas and touches upon the issues of their uniqueness, development and preservation. A study was conducted here on the example of the territory of the old city part of Tashkent, the main ways of development and preservation of the mahallas of the old city were identified.

Kalit so'z

Old city, mahalla, residential buildings, dead ends, sustainable urban development.

Introduction. The Old City in Tashkent is an archetypal example of carpet development, a common feature of historical districts across Central Asia. A makhalla is a traditional form of urban organisation that encompasses labyrinthine networks of narrow streets, residential houses with courtyards, public edifices, and mosques.[1] The entire neighbourhood presents a complex pattern of closely adjacent houses and buildings, forming a distinctive 'carpet' of structures. Such development has deep historical roots and reflects the particular characteristics of the local population's way of life. The dwellings are typically constructed using traditional materials such as clay and brick, which helps to maintain a comfortable indoor climate. The courtyards serve as places for family gatherings, recreation and farming, creating a comfortable and private space for residents.

Main. Modern Tashkent is a city with two contrasting parts: the new and the old. The new part of the city began to take shape after Tashkent became part of the Russian Empire in the second half of the 19th century and the capital of the Turkestan Governorate. The construction of the new part of the city was based on the European architectural trends of the time, which resulted in spacious and straight streets, a regular layout network and buildings in the classical style.[2]

The boundary between the old and new parts of the city is the Anchor Canal. This canal actually divides the city into two different eras and styles. While in the new part the streets are straight and wide and the architecture is predominantly European, in the old part the winding streets of the mahallas, lively bazaars, narrow alleys and

majestic ancient mosques have been preserved, giving this part of the city a unique oriental flavour.

These architectural and cultural differences between old and new Tashkent not only emphasise the city's rich history, but also create a unique atmosphere that appeals to both locals and tourists seeking to immerse themselves in the authentic atmosphere of the old East.

General information on the Old City Mahallas:

The area is a marvellous combination of diverse topography and rich natural environment, which makes it unique and attractive to a wide range of people. The variety of landscapes ranges from flat, flat areas to rolling hills. These natural features favour the development of active tourism, hiking and cycling routes.

Particular attention is drawn to the water routes, along which there are picturesque green areas. Many species of trees and shrubs grow here. Such rich vegetation contributes to maintaining a favourable microclimate, oxygenates the air and creates comfortable conditions for outdoor recreation and hiking in the mahallas.

There is significant potential for the creation of mini-parks in the area, which opens up opportunities for its further improvement and development. The design and development of such parks will improve infrastructure, create new recreational facilities, and enhance the environmental and aesthetic value of the area. Mini-parks can include various thematic zones, playgrounds, sports facilities and picnic areas, making them attractive to different age groups and interests, creating an environment for residents.

Due to its natural diversity and development potential, this area can become a centre of attraction for tourists, environmentalists and outdoor enthusiasts. The implementation of projects to create mini-parks and improve infrastructure will help strengthen the human connection with nature, promote healthy lifestyles and preserve the natural heritage for future generations.

Road analyses:

Most of the roads in the old town are cul-de-sacs due to their carpeting, and this is exactly what needs to be preserved. This unique architectural element gives the city its distinctive character and authenticity, reflecting its history and culture. In addition to preserving cultural heritage, these cul-de-sacs provide quiet and cosy corners in the city where residents and visitors can enjoy peace and privacy and take a break from the hustle and bustle of the big city. Thus, the preservation of cul-de-sacs and carpet development in the old city plays an important role in maintaining its unique atmosphere and attractiveness to tourists and residents. In figure 1 considered road scheme in old city.[3]

Figure 1.

Dead ends in Guzarboshi mahalla in old city Tashkent.

The image shows that most of the roads in the old town are cul-de-sacs forming narrow streets. This particular architectural element does not just characterise the city, but is also its soul and identity. It is important to preserve this unique feature as it reflects the history and culture of the place, creating a unique atmosphere that attracts tourists and creates a sense of immersion in the past.

The preservation of cul-de-sacs and narrow streets is important for the preservation of the authenticity of the urban character. These streets are often key architectural elements that convey the unique character of old urban areas. They create a cosy atmosphere, give the city a unique charm and attract the attention of visitors looking for authentic historical sites.

Moreover, the preservation of cul-de-sacs and narrow streets contributes to the historic value of the city. These streets can be artefacts of the past preserved in the present and are part of the heritage to be passed on to future generations. Therefore, their preservation not only preserves the uniqueness of the urban landscape, but also helps to preserve historical memory and cultural heritage.

Moreover, the preservation of cul-de-sacs and narrow streets contributes to the preservation of the natural and cultural environment. They create unique microclimatic conditions, providing coolness and shade on hot days, and can serve as a place for socialising, rest and relaxation. Therefore, the preservation of these narrow streets not only contributes to the preservation of the image of the city, but also creates comfortable and harmonious conditions for the life and recreation of its residents.

Residential buildings analyses:

A traditional Uzbek residential building is a closed, individual property with its own farm. It typically consists of a courtyard with a garden, living rooms with ayvans and office premises. The typology of the Tashkent residential building was influenced by the multivariate method of folk construction of the cities of the Ferghana Valley and Kashgar. This involved the construction of an open courtyard, an open ivan in front of

the house, a winter ivan–dahliz with lifting shutters-ravon, which allowed the room to be opened or closed if necessary, and finally, residential warm winter rooms-khona. However, in contrast to other cities in Tashkent, a more flexible housing layout was employed, with no clear orientation of the sides, a rectangular courtyard shape, and a one-story perimeter building. The second floor above the living rooms was rarely constructed and was predominantly an open gallery. Instead, it was situated above the office premises, the darvozakhona or the passages (dolon) and was utilised as a warehouse or hayloft. The facade of the house was constructed in the form of a two-storey solid volume, a technique that is characteristic of Tashkent apartment buildings.[1]

The dwelling in Tashkent was based on two enclosed spaces and one open space, which were arranged along a longitudinal or transverse axis. Additionally, they could be positioned at an angle, which gave rise to novel spatial solutions. An open room, known as a terrassa, was an indispensable feature of a residential building in Tashkent. It was located adjacent to the mehmonkhona (living room).

One of the planning features of residential areas in Tashkent, which were influenced by the norms of Muslim life, was the division of the courtyard into two halves. The smaller area, which was occupied by the men's quarters, had a connection with the street, while the larger, The inner area was occupied by the women's quarters, which were designated as the ichkari. The traditional residential architecture of Tashkent in the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. In contrast to the monumental public buildings, whose walls were constructed from burnt brick, the walls of residential buildings were typically constructed using a light wooden frame, with the filling of raw bricks or covered with clods of clay – goal. These structures were made from poles, beams, bundles of reeds and a variety of weaves. The frame structure was primarily influenced by the high seismicity of the region, providing the building with strength and enabling the rapid restoration of collapsed adobe wall fragments in the event of minor damage. The walls of the residential building, comprising a single- or double-row frame, attained a thickness of 40-60 cm, thereby serving as an effective thermal insulator. Single-frame walls were employed in the construction of douvals and utility rooms, while double-frame walls were utilised in residential, guest rooms and iwans. The double-row frame of the walls permitted the incorporation of niches within them. The walls were plastered with a solution of clay and ganch (a type of rough plaster) and then ganch, which gave them a decorative finish. This was often very rich, especially in rooms and terraces intended for receiving guests. It was obligatory that the doors and windows of the premises faced the courtyard.[1]

Landscape organization of the territory of old city mahallas:

The Old Town part of Tashkent is a unique landscape rich in history and cultural heritage. A variety of architectural styles can be found in this part of the city, reflecting the rich history of the city and its multinational population.

The landscape of the old part of Tashkent includes narrow streets, ancient buildings, mosques, mausoleums and other historical monuments. The buildings often

have a traditional oriental style with decorations made of ceramics and wood carvings. The narrow streets create a cosy and atmospheric environment, attracting tourists and residents with their ancient charm.

One of the characteristic features of the landscape of old Tashkent is the presence of many hidden courtyards, which are oases of peace and quiet in the heart of the city's bustle. These courtyards are often decorated with fountains, plants and traditional Uzbek architecture, creating unique and cosy corners for relaxation and socialising.

The landscape of the Old Town part of Tashkent also reflects the city's long history as a trading and cultural centre on the Great Silk Road. This historical context adds to the unique character and charm of this part of the city, making it an attractive place to explore and visit.

Conclusion.

In sum, the preservation of the Old City part of Tashkent is a vital step in maintaining the cultural and historical heritage of the city. The Old City is a unique complex of architectural, historical and cultural monuments that are an integral part of Tashkent's identity. The preservation of these areas contributes to strengthening the intergenerational link, ensuring the transmission of knowledge and traditions from ancestors to descendants. The preservation of the Old City part of Tashkent is necessary not only to maintain the cultural and historical heritage of the city, but also for its economic and social development. These mahallas represent living history, which is important to preserve and pass on to future generations. The preservation and development of old mahallas allows creating a harmonious combination of tradition and modernity, ensuring the sustainable development of the city and improving the quality of life of its residents.[3]

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